

Donor Properties of 1-Amidino-O-alkylurea: Part X. Dipyridine Bis 1-Amidino-O-alkylurea Cobalt(III) and Related Complexes

R. L. Dutta* and A. Syamal

Synthetic routes to dipyridine bis 1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt (III) complexes are described. These are obtained by oxidising yellow, unstable bis 1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt(II) complexes in presence of pyridine by a brisk current of air. A number of salts of the complex cations has been described. These are in general deep rose red to dull rose coloured. Conductance values indicate dissociation in dilute aqueous solution. Equivalent weight values are normal. Electronic absorption spectra shows the usual two ligand field bands around $29,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and around $20,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$

Di- β -picoline bis 1-amidino-O-alkylurea and di-acetonitrile bis 1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt (III) complexes have also been synthesised. These resemble closely the dipyridine bis-1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt (III) complexes in colour, conductance and in absorption spectra.

Chemical evidence points to trans disposition of the two unidentate ligands.

In a series of articles, we are presenting the results of our studies on the bis 1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt(III) complexes. Since the ligands, 1-amidino-O-alkylureas have a great similarity to biguanides and guanylureas², in so far as their complexing ability is concerned, we have undertaken comprehensive experiments to explore the arena of such similarities pertaining to cobalt(III). We have discussed our results with respect to the diammine bis 1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt (III) in the preceding paper. A large number of salts were described, the complex cations exhibiting varying degrees of protonation so that these had different electrolytic natures. The complexes have been tentatively assigned a trans structure. A comparison between the diammine bis biguanide cobalt(III) and the dipyridine bis biguanide cobalt(III) reveals that the dipyridine derivative is stabler in so far as the hydrolytic rupture is concerned. Unlike the diammine derivative, the dipyridine derivative did not change over to the hydroxo-aquo bis biguanide cobalt(III) complex, even on prolonged agitation with air³. Although the diammine bis biguanide cobalt(III) complexes have been characterised in cis as well as trans isomeric forms⁴, the dipyridine derivative so far has been known in one form³. All these above considerations led to the present investigation in pyridine and other similar coordinating solvents.

The bis 1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt(II) complexes are relatively unstable in moist condition and can be easily oxidised in the presence of pyridine and other such donor solvents to a dipyridine cobalt(III) complex or a related one. These have been obtained in the form of rose coloured crystalline products, sometimes giving cations of different

*Present address: Dept. of Chemistry, Ohio State University, Columbus, Ohio 43210, U.S.A.

1. R. L. Dutta and P. Rây, *this Journal*, 1959, **36**, 499.
2. R. L. Dutta and P. Rây, *this Journal*, 1959, **36**, 569, 576.
3. S. P. Ghosh and J. N. Gupta, *this Journal*, 1956, **33**, 193.
4. R. L. Dutta and S. Sarkar, *this Journal*, 1967, **44**, 853.

ionic natures. A number of salts, namely chloride, bromide, iodide, sulphate, thiosulphate, dithionate, oxalate, nitrate, cobaltinitrite etc. have been isolated and adequately characterised through analysis. Conductance measurements have been completed at various dilutions to evaluate the molar conductance values. These values at high dilutions are indicative of some dissociation—although a major contribution to the high values is made by the relatively high temperature ruling at the time of measurements. These values are almost in the same order as for the dipyridino bis biguanide cobalt(III) complexes³ ($\Lambda \infty$ (mean) = 156.3 mhos for $[\text{Co}(\text{Py})_2(\text{BigH})_2](\text{NO}_3)_3$ at 35°C, whereas $\Lambda \infty$ (mean) for the various dipyridine bis 1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt(III) complexes varies from 152 mhos to 168 mhos at 33.5°C (BigH = a molecule of biguanide).

TABLE I

Electrolytic conductance studies at 33.5°

Complex	Dilution (litres)	64	128	256	512	1024
1. $[\text{Co}(\text{Py})_2(\text{AMUN})_2](\text{NO}_3)_3$ 5H ₂ O	Λ_v	122.0	133.0	151.0	161.8	174.0
	$\Lambda \infty$	153.5	157.3	170.5	176.5	185.0
	$\Lambda \infty$ (mean)	168.5 mhos				
	Λ_M	505.5 mhos cm ² mole ⁻¹				
		Equivalent conductivity at infinite dilution*	Equivalent conductivity at infinite dilution*		Molar conductivity	
		$\Lambda \infty$ (mean), mhos		Λ_M , mhos cm ² mole ⁻¹		
2. $[\text{Co}(\text{Py})_2(\text{AEUH})_2](\text{NO}_3)_3$			167.3		501.9	
3. $[\text{Co}(\text{Py})_2(\text{AMU})_2]\text{I}$			158.5		158.5	
4. $[\text{Co}(\text{Py})_2(\text{AP}^i\text{U})(\text{AP}^i\text{UH})]\text{I}_2$			156.1		312.2	
5. $[\text{Co}(\text{Py})_2(\text{AB}^i\text{UH})_2]\text{I}_3$			154.9		464.7	
6. $[\text{Co}(\text{Py})_2(\text{Ab}^i\text{UH})_2](\text{NO}_3)_3$			153.5		460.5	
7. $[\text{Co}(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_2(\text{AEUH})_2]\text{I}_3$			152.5		457.5	

*The equivalent conductivity at infinite dilution was calculated by the use of Walden's formula $\Lambda \infty = \Lambda_v (1 + 0.692 \times n_1 \times n_2 \times v^{-\frac{1}{2}})$ where n_1 is the valence of the cation and n_2 is the valence of the anion.

These values are also comparable to the trans diammine complexes described earlier, for which the values varied within the range 144 mhos to 162 mhos. These values again, are somewhat lower than what has been reported for the trans diammine bis biguanide cobalt (III) complexes (Λ_{1024} is 178.8 mhos at 33°C). The ionic nature of the different type of complexes has also been adequately established from the molar conductance values, as compared to the reported ranges for such electrolytes⁵.

We then sought to establish the spatial relation of the two pyridine groups around cobalt(III) inside the complex. Various chemical reactions were tried to ascertain this point. The complex base was neutralised in the cold with oxalic acid to provide the dipyridine bis 1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt(III)-oxalate, instead of any oxalato bis 1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt(III) oxalate. Indeed we left the solution after neutralisation with oxalic acid for sufficient hours with no separation of the oxalato oxalate salt. Besides, treatment with sodium thiosulphate and a trace of acid failed to produce the thiosulphato

bridged 1-amidino-O-alkylurea complex. For the diammine bis biguanide series, these reactions indeed clinched the issue and decided the cis-trans isomerisms^{6,7}. Thus whereas the cis isomer gave positive results in the above reactions the trans did not give the oxalato oxalate salt or the thiosulphate bridged complex. The trans $[\text{Co}(\text{Py})_{12}(\text{BigH})_2]^{13}$ did not provide the oxalato-oxalate in the cold though the thiosulphate bridged complex was obtained with excess of $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ in the cold³. Besides these two reactions, we had also investigated the action of other powerful bidentate ligands (such as ortho-phenanthroline, α - α' -dipyridyl etc.) on this dipyridine complex. No reaction was found to occur in the cold. However, on warming on a steam bath there does occur pyridine evolution and ultimately the corresponding heterochelates can be isolated. This is parallel to what has been observed in our Laboratory with regard to the cis and trans diammine bis biguanide cobalt(III) complexes⁸.

Finally absorption spectra of all the representative members were recorded in aqueous solution. Spectra may be considered to be a powerful tool while distinguishing cis-trans isomers in the $[\text{Co} \text{A}_4 \text{B}_2]$ series where A and B are far off in the spectrochemical series. Thus this has been found to be very useful in the dihalogeno, dihalogeno acetato, azido-

CHART I

AAUH = 1-amidino-O-alkylurea.

Synthesis and reactions of dipyridine, di- β -picoline, diacetonitrile-bis 1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt (III) complexes.

chloro, azido-thiocyanato and dithiourea bis ethylenediamine cobalt(III) series⁹⁻¹¹. In all such cases, the trans isomer shows a further split of the long wave length band, producing

6. P. Rây and S. P. Ghosh, *this Journal*, 1942, **19**, 1.
7. P. Rây and A. N. Mazumdar, *this Journal*, 1946, **23**, 73.
8. R. L. Dutta and S. Sarkar, *this Journal*, 1967, **44**, 832.
9. K. Kuroda and P. S. Gentile, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, **27**, 153, 1289.
10. Idem, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1965, **38**, 1368.
11. W. A. Baker and E. M. Gaessar, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1963, **25**, 1161.

a total of three absorption bands compared to the two of the *cis*. Ours was even more difficult because, we had so far succeeded in obtaining only one variety. All such measurements reveal only two absorption bands around $29,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the other around $20,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

TABLE II

Electronic absorption spectral values

Complex	Band II		Band I	
	Wave number cm^{-1}	Molar absorptivity $\text{litre}^{-1}\text{mole}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$	Wave number cm^{-1}	Molar absorptivity $\text{litre}^{-1}\text{mole}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$
1. $[\text{Co}(\text{Py})_2(\text{AMUH})_2](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5}$ H_2O	30,000	386	20,100- 19,800	117
2. $[\text{Co}(\text{Py})_2(\text{AEUH})_2](\text{NO}_3)_3$	29,000- 28,600	280	20,400- 20,000	117
3. $[\text{Co}(\text{Py})_2(\text{AP}^i\text{UH})_2]\text{Br}_3$	29,000- 28,600	475	20,100- 19,800	105
4. $[\text{Co}(\text{Py})_2(\text{AB}^n\text{UH})_2](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5}$ $1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	29,000- 28,600	368	20,400- 20,000	135
5. $[\text{Co}(\text{Py})_2(\text{AB}^i\text{UH})_2](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5}$	29,000- 28,600	326	20,400- 20,000	93
6. $[\text{Co}(\text{Py})_2(\text{AA}^i\text{UH})_2](\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_{1.5}$	29,000- 28,600	198	20,000- 19,800	151
7. $[\text{Co} \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}(\beta\text{-Pic})_2(\text{AP}^i\text{UH})_2](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5}$	29,000- 28,600	437	20,000- 19,800	110
8. $[\text{Co}(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_2(\text{AEUH})_2](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5}$ $2\text{CH}_3\text{CN} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	28,600- 28,200	186	20,800	180

where Py=pyridine; β -Pic=beta-picoline; AMUH=1-amidino-O-methylurea; AEUH=1-amidino-O-ethylurea; APⁱUH=1-amidino-O-isopropylurea; ABⁱUH=1-amidino-O-isobutylurea; ABⁿUH=1-amidino-O-n-butylurea and AAⁱUH=1-amidino-O-isoamylurea.

We have observed two such bands in the case of our diammine complex too. The two bands are assigned the ligand field transitions ${}^1T_{1g} \leftarrow {}^1A_{1g}$ and ${}^1T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^1A_{1g}$. Whereas the

where X=univalent anion.

absorption bands in the long wave length region appear to be shifted slightly towards lower energy side in the pyridine complexes than in the diammine complexes. Summing all these evidences at our disposal, we attach tentatively a trans configuration to our products.

The reactions were extended to beta-picoline and also to acetonitrile. Whereas the beta-picoline complexes are extremely close to the pyridine analogues in their behaviour, reactivity, conductance, absorption spectra, the parent acetonitrile complex the sulphate salt crystallises with two moles of acetonitrile along with some water of crystallisation. This has been proved through analytical studies on the sample after air drying and after heating to 120°C when acetonitrile of crystallisation was lost. Otherwise these run parallel to the pyridine series in conductance, absorption spectra etc. α -Picoline d'd not furnish well defined, crystalline materials, which might be ascribed to the possible steric hindrance of the α -methyl group.

The equivalent weights of all the principal types were determined by running them through a strong cation exchanger (H^+ form) and finally titrating the liberated acid. The values, thus obtained support the results deduced from the analytical figures and conductance results.

TABLE III
Equivalent weight values

Complex	Found	Required*
1. $[Co(Py)_2(AMUH)_2](SO_4)_{1.5} \cdot H_2O$	199	203
2. (a) $[Co(Py)_2(AEUEH)_2](SO_4)_{1.5}$	201	207
(b) $[Co(Py)_2(AEUEH)_2](NO_3)_3$	213	221
3. (a) $[Co(Py)_2(AP^iUH)_2](SO_4)_{1.5}$	210	216
(b) $[Co(Py)_2(AP^iUH)_2](C_2O_4)_{1.5} \cdot 3H_2O$	240	230
4. (a) $[Co(Py)_2(AB^oUH)_2](SO_4)_{1.5} \cdot 1.5H_2O$	230	234
(b) $[Co(Py)_2(AB^oUH)_2](NO_3)_3$	235	239
(c) $[Co(Py)_2(AB^iUH)_2](SO_4)_{1.5}$	220	225
5. (a) $[Co(Py)_2(AA^iUH)_2](SO_4)_{1.5}$	230	235
(b) $[Co(Py)_2(AA^iUH)_2](C_2O_4)_{1.5}$	225	231
6. $[Co(\beta-Pic)_2(AEUEH)_2](SO_4)_{1.5}$	220	261
7. $[Co(\beta-Pic)_2(AP^iUH)_2](SO_4)_{1.5} \cdot 7H_2O$	261	267

*These values have been deduced on the basis of elemental analysis and conductance measurements.

We would like to record that in the diammine series, we observed that the visible red or orange red colour of the complex changed overnight to a fine violet one, which was traced to a significant change of the absorption spectra in the high energy side. As a contrast to this we observed here that the dipyridine bis-1-amidino-O-methylurea (and also the ethyl derivative) cobalt(III) sulphate solution d'd not show any such change in 24 hours. Thus the conversion of the dipyridine complex to a hydroxo aquo complex is far slower than in the case of the diammine complex. So, the hydrolytic rupture is much less in the dipyridine series. In this regard these complexes resemble very closely the dipyridine bis-biguamide cobalt(III) compounds.³

Mention may also be made here of concerted trials given to crystallise the salts with optically active anions. Unfortunately, none of the chloride-d-tartrate, pure d-tartrate or the d-camphor-10-sulphonate could be prepared, so that our desire to attempt resolution of the complex did not materialise.

EXPERIMENTAL

l-amidino-O-methylurea, l-amidino-O-ethylurea, l-amidino-O-n-butylurea, l-amidino-O-isobutylurea and l-amidino-O-isoamylurea sulphates were prepared and purified according to published procedure¹. Preparation of l-amidino-O-isopropylurea sulphate was described in the preceding part of this series.

The complexes described below are in general soluble in water and insoluble in alcohol. The iodide, hydroxide and cobaltinitrite salts have reasonable solubility in both water and alcohol. All these complexes were dried in air. As the length of the alkyl group in the l-amidino-O-alkylureas increased, the solubility of the dipyridine complexes decreased, so that isolation became easier. Cooling in ice for one to three hours appeared favourable.

Complexes of O-methylurea: Dipyridine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) sulphate.— $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2.8 g) and l-amidino-O-methylurea sulphate (3.6 g) were dissolved in water (15 ml), pyridine (5 ml) was added and a brisk current of air was passed for one hour during which time rose red crystals separated. These were filtered and washed with spirit. This gives alkaline reaction. The substance liberates pyridine when heated in a dry test tube or with dilute alkali. This compound may also be prepared by air oxidation of cobalt(II) bis l-amidino-O-methylurea in presence of pyridine followed by neutralisation with dilute H_2SO_4 in the cold.

Dipyridine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) iodide: The filtrate from the above reaction was treated with a concentrated solution of KI and cooled in a frigidaire for one day. The crystals separated were filtered and washed with ice cold spirit. This gives an alkaline reaction.

Dipyridine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) tri iodide. $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2.4 g) and l-amidino-O-methylurea sulphate (3.6 g) were dissolved in water (10 ml) and liquor ammonia (10 ml) was added. The yellow cobaltous complex formed was filtered quickly and washed with ice cold water until free from ammonia. The cobaltous complex was oxidised by passing a brisk current of air for one and a half hour in presence of pyridine (10 ml) to a dark red solution. This was filtered and neutralised with 2N HCl. A concentrated solution of KI was added to this and cooled in ice. The crystals separated were filtered and washed with ice cold spirit.

The corresponding bromide, thiosulphate and dithionate were prepared similarly as tri iodide but a concentrated solution of KBr, $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ or BaS_2O_6 respectively was added in lieu of KI.

Dipyridine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) nitrate.—The dark red solution of the complex base was neutralised with dilute HNO_3 and allowed to evaporate at room

temperature. A pasty mass separated and was taken up with acetone and scratched. The crystals separated were filtered, sucked well and dried in a desiccator. The substance is soluble in water and alcohol.

Dipyridine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) cobaltinitrite was prepared by metathetic reaction between the sulphate and a concentrated solution of $\text{Na}_3[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_6]$ in presence of pyridine.

Dipyridine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) oxalate.—The dark red solution of the complex base was neutralised with dilute oxalic acid in the cold and kept in the frigidaire for one day. The rose red crystals separated were filtered and washed with spirit.

Oxalato bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) oxalate. The dark red solutions of the complex base was neutralised with dilute oxalic acid and heated on the steam bath in presence of a slight acid. The colour of the solution gradually changed from orange to deep violet and pyridine was disengaged. When the evolution of pyridine ceased, the solution was cooled and deep violet crystals separated. These were filtered and washed with spirit. This compound was also obtained by heating the aqueous solution of the complex oxalate at the temperature of steam bath in presence of slight acid. It is sparingly soluble in water.

Complexes of O-ethylurea: Dipyridine bis 1-amidino-O-ethylurea cobalt(III) sulphate: $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2.4 g) and 1-amidino-O-ethylurea sulphate (3.6 g) were dissolved in water (10 ml), liquor ammonia (10 ml) was added. The yellow cobaltous complex formed was filtered and washed with ice cold water until free from ammonia. The cobaltous complex was oxidised by passing a brisk current of air for one and half hour in presence of pyridine (10 ml) to a dark red solution. This was filtered and neutralised with 2N H_2SO_4 in the cold. The rose red crystals were filtered and washed with spirit. The substance liberates pyridine from dilute alkali. The compound does not lose pyridine at 100° .

The iodide and the other salts were prepared as crystalline products by neutralising the complex base with 2N HCl and then salting out with KI, KBr, $\text{Na}_3[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_6]$, $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ or $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_6$ as the case may be. The nitrate and the oxalate salts were obtained by neutralisation of the dark red solution of the complex base with dilute HNO_3 and oxalic acid respectively in the cold.

Complexes of other O-alkylureas: Dipyridine bis 1-amidino-O-isopropylurea cobalt(III) hydroxide.—The dark red solution of the complex base obtained similarly as in the case of 1-amidino-O-ethylurea, was cooled in ice for few hours. The brownish red crystals separated were filtered, sucked well and dried in a desiccator over solid KOH.

The other complexes were prepared by adopting procedures similar to the O-ethylurea derivatives.

Analytical results are included in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Analysis and Colour of Cobalt(III) Complexes

Complex	Colour	Co %	N %	Anion %
1. [Co (Py) ₂ (AMUH) ₂] (SO ₄) _{1.5} ·H ₂ O	Rose red	Found: 9.4 Reqd: 9.6	22.9	23.2 23.5
2. [Co (Py) ₂ (AMU) ₂]I	Brownish red	Found: 10.5 Reqd:] 10.3	24.2	22.5 22.2
3. [Co(Py) ₂ (AMUH) ₂]I ₃	Brownish red	Found: 7.2 Reqd: 7.1	16.6	45.8 45.9
4. [Co (Py) ₂ (AMUH) ₂]Br ₃ ·H ₂ O	Rose red	Found: 8.5 Reqd: 8.3	19.6	34.4 33.9
5. [Co (Py) ₂ (AMUH) ₂] (S ₂ O ₆) _{1.5} ·2H ₂ O	Rose red	Found: 8.2 Reqd: 8.1	19.2	—
6. [Co(Py) ₂ (AMU) (AMUH)](S ₂ O ₃) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Rose red	Found: 10.0 Reqd: 9.8	23.3	18.8 18.8
7. [Co(Py) ₂ (AMUH) ₂] (NO ₃) ₃ ·5H ₂ O	Rose red	Found: 7.8 Reqd: 8.1	25.0	—
8. [Co(Py) ₂ (AMUH) ₂] [Co (NO ₂) ₆]	Yellow	Found: 15.3 Reqd: 15.0	28.5	—
9. [Co(Py) ₂ (AMUH) ₂](C ₂ O ₄) _{1.5} ·H ₂ O	Rose red	Found: 9.6 Reqd: 9.8	23.2	—
10. [Co(C ₂ O ₄)(AMUH) ₂](C ₂ O ₄) _{0.5} ·0.5H ₂ O*	Deep violet	Found: 13.8 Reqd: 13.6	25.9	—
11. [Co(Py) ₂ (AEUH) ₂] (SO ₄) _{1.5}	Rose red	Found: 9.7 Reqd: 9.5	22.2	22.9 23.1
12. [Co(Py) ₂ (AEUH) ₂] I ₃	Brownish red	Found: 7.1 Reqd: 6.8	16.6	43.8 44.4
13. [Co(Py) ₂ (AEUH) ₂]Br ₃	Rose red	Found: 8.4 Reqd: 8.2	19.8	33.0 33.4
14. [Co(Py) ₂ (AEUH) ₂] [Co (NO ₂) ₆]	Yellow	Found: 14.8 Reqd: 14.5	28.0	—
15. [Co(Py) ₂ (AEUH) ₂] (S ₂ O ₃) _{1.5} ·0.5H ₂ O	Brownish red	Found: 9.2 Reqd: 9.0	21.1	25.0 25.6
16. [Co(Py) ₂ (AEUH) ₂] (S ₂ O ₆) _{1.5}	Rose red	Found: 8.4 Reqd: 8.2	19.2	—
17. [Co(Py) ₂ (AEUH) ₂] (NO ₃) ₃	Shining rose red	Found: 9.1 Reqd: 8.9	27.4	—
18. [Co(Py) ₂ (AEUH) ₂](C ₂ O ₄) _{1.5} ·3H ₂ O	Rose red	Found: 9.0 Reqd: 8.9	21.2	—
19. [Co(C ₂ O ₄) (AEUH) ₂](C ₂ O ₄) _{0.5} ·1.5H ₂ O**Violet	Violet	Found: 12.6 Reqd: 12.3	23.7	—
20. [Co(Py) ₂ (AP ⁱ UH) ₂] (OH) ₃	Brownish red	Found: 10.9 Reqd: 10.6	25.4	—
21. [Co (Py) ₂ (AP ⁱ UH) ₂] (SO ₄) _{1.5}	Rose red	Found: 9.1 Reqd: 9.0	21.6	22.4 22.1
22. [Co(Py) ₂ (AP ⁱ UH) ₂]Br ₃	Rose red	Found: 8.2 Reqd: 8.0	19.2	31.8 32.2
23. [Co(Py) ₂ (AP ⁱ U) (AP ⁱ UH)]I ₂	Brown	Found: 8.2 Reqd: 8.0	18.8	33.4 33.9
24. [Co(Py) ₂ (AP ⁱ UH) ₂](S ₂ O ₃) _{1.5} ·3H ₂ O	Rose red	Found 8.4 Reqd: 8.1	19.2	23.0 23.1

*Found: H₂O (by loss at 110°C), 2.7%, Reqd: .21%.**Found: H₂O (by loss at 110°C), 6.0%, Reqd. 5.6%.

Complex	Colour	Co %	N %	Anion %
25. [Co(Py) ₂ (AP ⁱ UH) ₂] (S ₂ O ₆) _{1.5} .H ₂ O	Rose red	Found: 7.5 Reqd: 7.7	18.5 18.4	12.8(%S) 12.5
26. [Co(Py) ₂ (AP ⁱ UH) ₂][Co(NO ₂) ₆]	Yellow	Found: 13.8 Reqd: 14.0	26.5 26.6	—
27. [Co(Py) ₂ (AP ⁱ UH) ₂] (C ₂ O ₄) _{1.5} .3H ₂ O	Rose red	Found: 8.8 Reqd: 8.5	20.3 20.2	18.7 19.1
28. [Co(C ₂ O ₄)(AP ⁱ UH) ₂] (C ₂ O ₄) _{0.5} 4H ₂ O***	Violet	Found: 11.0 Reqd: 10.7	20.5 20.3	—
29. [Co(Py) ₂ (AB ^a UH) ₂](OH) ₃ .H ₂ O	Brownish red	Found: 10.0 Reqd: 9.8	23.1 23.2	—
30. [Co(Py) ₂ (AB ^a UH) ₂](SO ₄) _{1.5} .1.5H ₂ O	Rose red	Found: 8.4 Reqd: 8.3	19.6 19.8	20.8 20.4
31. [Co(Py) ₂ (AB ^a UH) ₂] Br ₃ H ₂ O	Rose red	Found: 7.6 Reqd: 7.4	17.9 17.7	30.0 30.3
32. [Co(Py) ₂ (AB ^a UH) ₂] (NO ₃) ₃	Rose red	Found: 8.3 Reqd: 8.2	25.3 25.3	—
33. [Co(Py) ₂ (AB ^a UH) ₂] (S ₂ O ₃) _{1.5} 2H ₂ O	Brownish red	Found: 19.1 Reqd: 19.0	21.6 21.2	—
34. [Co(Py) ₂ (AB ^a UH) ₂] (S ₂ O ₆) _{1.5}	Rose red	Found: 7.8 Reqd: 7.6	18.4 18.1	—
35. [Co(Py) ₂ (AB ^a UH) ₂] [Co(NO ₂) ₆]	Yellow	Found: 13.8 Reqd: 13.0	25.5 25.8	—
36. [Co(Py) ₂ (AB ^a UH) ₂] (C ₂ O ₄) _{1.5} .H ₂ O	Rose red	Found: 8.8 Reqd: 8.6	20.2 20.4	—
37. [Co(C ₂ O ₄)(AB ^a UH) ₂] C ₂ O ₄ 0.5	Violet	Found: 11.8 Reqd: 11.6	22.4 22.1	—
38. [Co(Py) ₂ (AB ⁱ UH) ₂] (SO ₄) _{1.5}	Rose red	Found: 8.7 Reqd: 8.7	20.6 20.6	21.4 21.2
39. [Co(Py) ₂ (AB ⁱ UH) ₂] I ₃	Brownish red	Found: 6.7 Reqd: 6.4	15.6 15.3	41.1 41.6
40. [Co(Py) ₂ (AB ⁱ UH) ₂]Br ₃	Rose red	Found: 17.2 Reqd: 17.3	17.2 17.3	30.3 29.6
41. [Co(Py) ₂ (AB ⁱ UH) ₂] (S ₂ O ₃) _{1.5} 3H ₂ O	Brownish red	Found: 8.0 Reqd: 7.8	18.4 18.5	22.2 22.2
42. [Co(Py) ₂ (AB ⁱ UH) ₂] [Co(NO ₂) ₆] 2H ₂ O	Yellow	Found: 13.3 Reqd: 13.0	25.0 24.7	—
43. [Co(Py) ₂ (AB ⁱ UH) ₂] (C ₂ O ₄) _{1.5}	Rose red	Found: 8.6 Reqd: 8.8	21.3 21.0	—
44. [Co(C ₂ O ₄)(AB ⁱ UH) ₂] (C ₂ O ₄) _{0.5}	Violet	Found: 11.8 Reqd: 11.6	22.3 22.1	—
45. [Co(Py) ₂ (AA ⁱ UH) ₂] (SO ₄) _{1.5}	Rose red	Found: 8.0 Reqd: 8.3	20.2 20.0	20.8 20.4
46. [Co(Py) ₂ (AA ⁱ UH) ₂] (S ₂ O ₃) _{1.5}	Rose red	Found: 8.2 Reqd: 8.0	19.5 19.2	23.0 23.0
47. [Co(Py) ₂ (AA ⁱ UH) ₂] (S ₂ O ₆) _{1.5} H ₂ O	Rose red	Found: 7.4 Reqd: 7.2	17.3 17.1	—
48. [Co(Py) ₂ (AA ⁱ UH) ₂] [Co(NO ₂) ₆] H ₂ O	Yellow	Found: 13.0 Reqd: 12.8	24.4 24.4	—
49. [Co(Py) ₂ (AA ⁱ UH) ₂] (C ₂ O ₄) _{1.5}	Rose red	Found: 8.4 Reqd: 8.5	20.5 20.2	19.4 19.0

***Found: H₂O (by loss at 110°C), 12.9. Reqd: 13.0%

Complex	Colour	Co %	N %	Anion %
50. $[\text{Co}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)(\text{AA}^i\text{UH})_2](\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_{0.5}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ****	Violet	Found: 10.5 Reqd: 10.6	20.1 20.2	
51. $[\text{Co}(\beta\text{-Pic})_2(\text{AEUH})_2](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5}$	Rose red	Found: 9.2 Reqd: 9.0	21.3 21.5	22.3 22.1
52. $[\text{Co}(\beta\text{-Pic})_2(\text{AEUH})_2][\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_6]\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Yellow	Found: 14.0 Reqd: 13.7	26.1 26.1	—
53. $[\text{Co}(\beta\text{-Pic})_2(\text{AEUH})_2](\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_{1.5}$	Brownish red	Found: — Reqd: —	20.4 20.7	25.4 25.0
54. $[\text{Co}(\beta\text{-Pic})_2(\text{AEUH})_2](\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_{1.5}$	Rose red	Found: 9.0 Reqd: 9.2	22.2 22.0	—
55. $[\text{Co}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)(\text{AEUH})_2](\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_{0.5}\cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Violet	Found: 12.6 Reqd: 12.3	23.7 23.4	—
(Prepared from 54)				
56. $[\text{Co}(\beta\text{-Pic})_2(\text{AP}^i\text{UH})_2](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5}\cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Rose red	Found: 7.1 Reqd: 7.3	17.8 17.4	17.7 17.9
57. $[\text{Co}(\beta\text{-Pic})_2(\text{AP}^i\text{UH})_2][\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_6]$	Yellow	Found: 13.8 Reqd: 13.6	25.7 25.8	—
58. $[\text{Co}(\beta\text{-Pic})_2(\text{AP}^i\text{UH})_2](\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_{1.5}\cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	Brownish red	Found: — Reqd: —	19.5 19.4	23.1 23.3
59. $[\text{Co}(\beta\text{-Pic})_2(\text{AP}^i\text{UH})_2](\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_{1.5}$	Rose red	Found: 8.7 Reqd: 8.8	20.8 21.0	—
60. $[\text{Co}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)(\text{AP}^i\text{UH})_2](\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_{0.5}\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Prepared from 59)	Violet	Found: 10.9 Reqd: 10.7	20.6 20.3	—
61. $[\text{Co}(\beta\text{-Pic})_2(\text{AB}^i\text{UH})_2](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5}\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Rose red	Found: 8.3 Reqd: 8.2	19.7 19.6	20.0 20.1
62. $[\text{Co}(\beta\text{-Pic})_2(\text{AB}^i\text{UH})_2](\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_{1.5}\cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Brownish red	Found: — Reqd: —	18.6 18.5	22.7 22.3
63. $[\text{Co}(\beta\text{-Pic})_2(\text{AB}^i\text{UH})_2][\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_6]$	Yellow	Found: 13.1 Reqd: 13.1	25.2 25.0	
64. $[\text{Co}(\beta\text{-Pic})_2(\text{AB}^i\text{UH})_2](\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_{1.5}\cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	Rose red	Found: 8.5 Reqd: 8.3	19.4 19.6	
65. $[\text{Co}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)(\text{AB}^i\text{UH})_2](\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_{0.5}$ (Prepared from 64)	Violet	Found: 11.8 Reqd: 11.6	22.2 22.0	—
66. $[\text{Co}(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_2(\text{AEUH})_2](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5}\cdot 2\text{CH}_3\text{CN}\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}^{\dagger}$	Orange red	Found: 8.6 Reqd: 8.8	25.6 25.3	21.4 21.7
		Found: — ‡Reqd: —	26.0 25.7	—
67. $[\text{Co}(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_2(\text{AEUH})_2][\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_6]\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Yellow	Found: 15.2 Reqd: 15.0	28.4 28.3	—
68. $[\text{Co}(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_2(\text{AEUH})_2](\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_{1.5}\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Rose red	Found: 9.8 Reqd: 10.0	24.3 23.8	—
69. $[\text{Co}(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_2(\text{AEUH})_2]\text{I}_3$	Rose red	Found: — Reqd: —	17.6 17.9	48.6 48.7

****Found: H_2O (by loss at 110°C), 3.8. Reqd: 3.2%.

†Found: loss at 120° , 17.6. Reqd. 17.7%

‡Analysis for the product obtained after heating at 120°

The experimental procedure as described in Part IX was followed here.

This is a pleasure to acknowledge our indebtedness to C.S.I.R. for financial assistance to one of us (A.S.). We express our indebtedness also to Prof. Santi Ranjan Palit for his interest in our scheme. We thank Prof. S. K. Siddhanta for the encouragement given us. We gratefully acknowledge the generous gift of dicyandiamide by the American Cyanamide Company. We record with appreciation the services received from Mr. M. Sadhu while setting up the semimicro Duma combustion train.

INORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORIES,
THE UNIVERSITY OF BURDWAN,
BURDWAN, WEST BENGAL.
INDIA

Received, May 16, 1960.